

Electrochemical and spectroscopic studies on the interaction between copper(II) complex of Schiff base ligand and DNA

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([CuL(C₆H₅N₂O₂) (ClO₄)₂.H₂O, CuL) (L = *N*-(5-sulfosalicylidene)-4'-nitraniline) can strongly bind to DNA. The interaction between CuL and salmon sperm DNA in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NaOAc-HOAc (pH 4.8) has been investigated by cyclic voltammetry and UV/Vis spectroscopy. The observed oxidative peak for the central copper ion of CuL from cyclic voltammogram is shown at the glassy carbon electrode. It has been found that the oxidative peak current decreased significantly with increasing concentrations of DNA. In addition, the absorbance of CuL at its absorption peaks also decreased in the presence of DNA. All experimental results indicate that CuL can bind to DNA to form a 1 : 1 association complex with the binding constant of 1.05 × 10⁵ L mol⁻¹, and the major binding mode of CuL to DNA is "electrostatic binding".

Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) is the most important germ plasm of most organisms. It plays an important role in the process of storing, copying and transmitting germ messages. The recognition that DNA serves as a target for natural and artificial molecules in the inhibition of cellular disorders and in therapy of certain diseases is of paramount importance in inorganic biochemistry. The binding of small molecules, especially transition metal complexes to DNA and molecular identification are important in life science¹ and it is helpful to understand the way of the interaction between small molecules and DNA. Many metal complexes have anticarcinogenic properties. Among these compounds much attention has been paid to the complexes such as Fe[EDTA]²⁻, Cu(phen)₂²⁺, RuNi binuclear complex, dicyclopentadienyliron etc. They have the ability of splitting DNA and distinguishing DNA²⁻⁴. Furthermore, copper complexes including Cu(II)₂(salicylate)₄ and Cu(II)₂(3, 5-DIPS)₄ having SOD-mimetic activity lead to conclusions that copper complexes might have anticancer activity⁵. These complexes decreased tumor growth, metastasis and increased survival of tumor-bearing mice. An action mechanism of copper complexes as anticancer has been suggested to involve glutathione oxidation and accumulation of H₂O₂.

However, in recent years, the researches directed towards the isolation and evaluation of naturally occurring DNA cleaving agents and towards the design and synthesis of model compounds that can (specifically) cleave DNA be-

come more and more important. These compounds have become the indispensable tools for analyzing DNA structure, sequencing DNA molecules, isolating and cloning genes. Copper complexes of synthetic ligands appear to be promising chemical/artificial nucleases⁷. Studies on metal complexes of nitrogen-containing ligands, especially heteroaromatic nitrogen bases are of much interest.

In this paper, CuL we studied is a kind of copper complex with Schiff base ligand, so we have conducted experiments on the interaction of CuL with DNA by electrochemical and spectroscopic methods. The experimental results have proved that CuL can interact with DNA mainly by "electrostatic binding". This conclusion would surely bring detailed insight into the action mechanism of CuL with DNA and provide useful message for designing new and efficient drugs as disease diagnosis and chemotherapeutic agents.

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents :

CHI832 electrochemical analyzer was produced by Shanghai Chenhua Instrument Company of China; the three-electrode system was composed of a glassy carbon electrode (GCE, Φ 3 mm) as working electrode, a Ag/AgCl as the reference electrode and a platinum electrode as auxiliary electrode; Cary 50 UV/Vis spectrophotometer was produced by Varian Company of Australian; 510 P FT-IR spectrometer was produced by Nicolet Company of the United

States; pHs-25 pH meter was produced by Shanghai Leici Instrument Factory of China.

Salmon sperm DNA was purchased from Shanghai Huashun Biologic Engineering Company, its concentration was determined by the ultraviolet absorption at 260 nm ($\epsilon = 6600 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), used without further purification. CuL was supplied by Department of Chemistry, East China Normal University. $1.48 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ solution of CuL was prepared by dissolving 0.105 g CuL in 10 ml doubly deionized water. 0.1 mol L^{-1} NaOAc-HOAc, HOAc, pH 4.8, was used as buffer solution. The other reagents were all analytical reagents prepared with doubly deionized water.

Experimental method :

Electrochemical studies of the interaction between CuL and DNA :

Different volume of $1.48 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ CuL was added to 5 ml of 0.1 mol L^{-1} NaOAc-HOAc buffer solution (pH 4.8). The cyclic voltammograms (CV) of the solutions were recorded on CHI832 electrochemical analyzer. Then different volume of $4.68 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ DNA were added to the solution followed by recording CV. The potential scanning range is from -0.6 V to 0.8 V . The scanning rate is 0.1 V s^{-1} ; the sample interval is 0.001 V and the quiet time 2 s.

UV/Vis studies of the interaction between CuL and DNA :

$40 \mu\text{L}$ of $1.48 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ CuL and $20 \mu\text{L}$ of $4.68 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ DNA solution were in turn added to 10 ml colorimetric tubes respectively; then diluted to the desired scale with 0.1 mol L^{-1} NaOAc-HOAc buffer solution, the solutions were kept for 6 min at room temperature to react completely. The UV/Vis spectra of CuL were recorded on a Cary 50 spectrophotometer in 1 cm quartz cuvettes. The range of the scanning wavelengths is from 200 nm to 800 nm.

Results and discussion

The structure and characterization of $[\text{CuL}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$:

The structure of $[\text{CuL}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ is as below :

The UV/Vis absorption spectra of $[\text{CuL}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ are as follows : Three absorption peaks for $[\text{CuL}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ were observed. The wavelengths are at 222.1 nm, 252.0 nm and 383.0 nm respectively. The peaks at 222.1 nm and 252.0 nm are caused by $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ electron transition of C=N and N=O respectively. While the peak at 383.0 nm is caused by $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ electron transition of C=N.

The IR absorption spectra of $[\text{CuL}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ are as follows : Two absorption bands at 3344 cm^{-1} , 3250 cm^{-1} are characteristic stretching vibration for O-H. The absorption band at 3412 cm^{-1} is the stretching vibration of N-H, and that at 1616 cm^{-1} , 1654 cm^{-1} are the stretching vibration of C=N and C=O respectively. Three absorption bands at 1514 cm^{-1} , 1584 cm^{-1} and 1463 cm^{-1} , respectively, are the stretching vibration of C=C in the aromatic ring. The absorption bands at 1193 cm^{-1} , 1030 cm^{-1} are the stretching vibration for S=O in sulfo group.

The result of the elemental analysis of $[\text{CuL}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)]^{2+}$ (L = N-(5-sulfosalicylidene)-4'-nitraniline) is as follows : C, 41.82%, 41.71%; H, 3.092%, 3.108%; N, 10.10%, 10.06%; TG (H_2O), 3.61%. The theoretical value is that : C, 42.18%; H, 3.174%; N, 10.36%; TG (H_2O), 3.33%.

Electrochemical studies of the interaction between CuL and DNA on the glassy carbon electrode :

Cyclic voltammograms of CuL before and after adding DNA were recorded to test whether CuL interact with DNA. The cyclic voltammograms of CuL at the glassy carbon electrode in 0.1 mol L^{-1} NaOAc-HOAc buffer solution (pH 4.8) were shown in Fig. 1. The curve 1 was the cyclic voltammogram of CuL solution in the absence of DNA, in which the observed oxidative peak potential (E_{pa}) was 0.012 V, the oxidative peak current (I_{pa}) was $1.36 \times 10^{-5} \text{ A}$. The curves 2~6 were the cyclic voltammograms of CuL in different concentrations of DNA. It was observed that the peak current of CuL greatly decreased with increasing concentrations of DNA, and the peak potential shifted to more positive value in the range of $0 \sim 1.40 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ DNA (Fig. 1, curves 1~4). However, when the DNA concentration was higher than $1.40 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, the peak potential shifted to more negative value (Fig. 1, curves 5~6). No new oxidation-reduction peaks appear after adding DNA. So CuL interacting with DNA forms electrochemically non-active complex, which results in a decrease of the equilibrium concentration of CuL as well as the peak current. It is generally accepted that there are three kinds of binding modes for small molecules to DNA, which refer to "intercalative binding", "groove binding" and "electrostatic

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of CuL with increasing concentrations of DNA $C_{CuL} : 1.92 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$; $C_{DNA} : (1) 0; (2) 9.36 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}; (3) 1.40 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1}; (4) 2.34 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1}; (5) 3.28 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1}; (6) 3.74 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$.

binding". According to Fig. 1 and the the molecular structure of CuL, it is reasonable that the major binding mode of CuL to DNA is "electrostatic binding", in which CuL binds to DNA through its cationic group $[CuL(C_6H_5N_2O_2)]^{2+}$ to PO_4^{3-} in backbone of DNA.

Effect of the scanning rate on the oxidative peak current (I_{pa}) of CuL : I_{pa} is directly proportional to the square root of the scanning rate in the range from 0.01 V s^{-1} to 0.25 V s^{-1} , with a regression equation, $Y = 37.609x - 1.9641$ and a correlation coefficient $R^2 = 0.9984$, where y is the I_{pa} value, x is the square root of the scanning rate. Fig. 2 is the plot of I_{pa} vs $v^{1/2}$ (v is the scanning rate), which is a straight line, indicating that the electrooxidation process of CuL is controlled by the diffusion of CuL.

Fig. 2. The relationship between the oxidation peak current of CuL and the scan rate $C_{CuL} : 5.92 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$.

Effect of the concentration of DNA on the oxidative peak current of CuL : The experiment that the concentrations of both dsDNA and ssDNA increased gradually while the concentration of CuL was unchanged was done. Fig. 3 showed the relationship between the oxidative peak current of CuL and DNA concentration. At the beginning, the peak current decreased obviously. When the concentration of DNA increased to a certain degree, the peak current reached a constant value. Eventually, the peak current decreased no longer, suggesting that the interaction of CuL with DNA was saturated. We have, $I_p = 269 n^{3/2} AD^{1/2} v^{1/2} C_0$.

The relationship between the peak current (I_p) and the diffusion coefficient (D) can be deduced. After adding DNA, the diffusion coefficient of the association complex (DNA-CuL) is much smaller than that of the free complex (CuL) when CuL bound to DNA, which results in the reduction of the diffusion velocity and the decrease of the peak current. The concentration of both dsDNA and ssDNA had obvious reduction effect on the peak current of CuL, indicating that CuL bind to DNA mainly through "electrostatic binding".

Fig. 3. Effect of the concentration of dsDNA (curve 1) and ssDNA (curve 2) on the oxidation peak current of CuL. $C_{CuL} : 1.78 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$.

Effect of pH on the interaction : I_{pa} increases with pH from 4.0, having a maximum value at pH 4.8, then decreases with further increase in pH to 5.5.

Effect of reaction time on the oxidation peak current of CuL : The oxidative peak current of CuL decreased gradually with increase in reaction time and attains a constant value after six minutes indicating completion of the reaction.

The binding ratio and the binding constant of the DNA-CuL association complex :

It is assumed that DNA and CuL only produce a single

complex DNA-*n* CuL :

The equilibrium constant can be expressed as follow,

$$\beta = \frac{[\text{DNA-}n\text{CuL}]}{[\text{DNA}][\text{CuL}]^n} \quad (1)$$

And the following equations can be deduced,

$$\Delta I_{\text{max}} = K' C_{\text{DNA}} \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta I = K' [\text{DNA-}n\text{CuL}] \quad (3)$$

$$[\text{DNA}] + [\text{DNA-}n\text{CuL}] = C_{\text{DNA}} \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta I_{\text{max}} - \Delta I = K' (C_{\text{DNA}} - [\text{DNA-}n\text{CuL}]) \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta I_{\text{max}} - \Delta I = K' [\text{DNA}] \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{1}{\Delta I} = \frac{1}{\Delta I_{\text{max}}} + \frac{1}{\beta \Delta I_{\text{max}} [\text{CuL}]^n} \quad (7)$$

With different *n*, there are different relationship curves between ΔI^{-1} and $[\text{CuL}]^{-n}$. According to eq. (7), the relationship curve between ΔI^{-1} and $[\text{CuL}]^{-n}$, with the suitable *n*, should be a straight line if there is only one complex was formed when CuL bound to DNA. From the slope and intercept of the straight line, the binding constant β can be calculated.

The dependence of the oxidation peak current for CuL in the absence or presence of DNA on the concentration of CuL was shown in Fig. 4. By calculating different ΔI (the difference of $I_{\text{pa}1}$ and $I_{\text{pa}2}$) and $[\text{CuL}]$ linear relation of ΔI^{-1} vs $[\text{CuL}]^{-n}$ was obtained. As for $n = 1$, the curve is a straight line ($R^2 = 0.9986$).

Fig. 4. The relationship between $I_{\text{pa}1}$, $I_{\text{pa}2}$, ΔI_{pa} and C_{CuL} . (1) $C_{\text{DNA}} = 0$; (2) $C_{\text{DNA}} = 1.87 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$; (3) $\Delta I_{\text{pa}} = I_{\text{pa}1} - I_{\text{pa}1}$.

For $n = 1/3$ and $1/2$, the curve bends up and down respectively. From the slope and intercept of the straight line, the binding constant β was calculated to be $1.05 \times 10^5 \text{ L mol}^{-1}$, which was corresponding to the equation $\text{DNA} + \text{CuL} \rightleftharpoons \text{DNA-CuL}$. This means that CuL bound to DNA to form a 1 : 1 association complex. In three kinds of interaction mode, the most possible mode for forming a 1 : 1 association complex is "electrostatic binding"⁹. In addition, the effect of the salt concentration of solution on binding constant was also investigated. It was observed that the binding constant increased with decrease in salt concentration. The salt effect is an important evidence for "electrostatic binding". Thus, the major interaction mode of CuL with DNA is "electrostatic binding".

UV/Vis spectroscopic studies of the interaction between CuL and DNA :

Hypochromism and red shift of the absorption bands are used to characterize the binding of small molecules to DNA¹⁰. In $0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ NaOAc-HOAc}$ buffer solution, the CuL spectra in the presence of DNA shows absorbance peaks at 222.1 nm, 252.0 nm and 383.0 nm respectively, all decreased with the addition of DNA, but no obvious red shift was observed. It is recognized that red shift of the absorption band is an important evidence for the intercalation of small molecules into DNA base stack¹¹, while the phenomena of hypochromic effect without shift are evidence for "electrostatic binding". Therefore, it can be deduced that CuL interact with DNA mainly by "electrostatic binding", which is consistent with the above electrochemical studies.

Conclusion :

The interaction between CuL and salmon sperm DNA was studied by cyclic voltammetry and UV/Vis spectroscopy. The oxidation peak current for CuL decreased with increasing concentrations of DNA. In addition, the absorbance of CuL decreased greatly with no shift of absorption peaks in the presence of DNA. The conclusion can be drawn that CuL could interact with DNA mainly by "electrostatic binding" and form a 1 : 1 DNA-CuL association complex with a binding constant of $1.05 \times 10^5 \text{ L mol}^{-1}$.

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